

Benefits of Nature Exposure

Greenwood, A., & Gatersleben, B. (2016). Let's go outside! Environmental restoration amongst adolescents and the impact of friends and phones.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0272494416300871>

Maas, J., Verheij, R. A., De Vries, S., Spreeuwenberg, P., Schellevis, F. G., & Groenewegen, P. P. (2009). Morbidity is related to a green living environment.

<https://jech.bmj.com/content/jech/63/12/967.full.pdf>

Benefits of Nature Prescriptions

Ivers, R., & Astell-Burt, T. (2023). Nature Rx: Nature prescribing in general practice.

<https://www1.racgp.org.au/getattachment/2c334572-88f7-4cc5-83dc-a860c4af4458/Nature-prescribing-in-general-practice.aspx>

Kondo, M. C., Oyekanmi, K. O., Gibson, A., South, E. C., Bocarro, J., & Hipp, J. A. (2020). Nature prescriptions for health: A review of evidence and research opportunities.

<https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/17/12/4213>

Nguyen, P. Y., Astell-Burt, T., Rahimi-Ardabili, H., & Feng, X. (2023). Effect of nature prescriptions on cardiometabolic and mental health, and physical activity: a systematic review.

<https://www.thelancet.com/action/showPdf?pii=S2542-5196%2823%2900025-6>